

Wf4Ever: Advanced Workflow Preservation Technologies for Enhanced Science

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D6.2: Final report on the creation of a Community of Users in Genomics

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Wf4Ever Consortium

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Change Log

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0.1	28-11-2013	Kristina Hettne	Created document
0.2	30-10-2013	Kristina Hettne	Revised table of contents after aligning with IAA and consulting ISOCO, wrote the introduction and added content bullet points for the other sections.
0.4	04-11-2013	Kristina Hettne	Wrote the executive summary, methodological approach, best practices for workflow design, community engagement activities, appendix A-C
0.5 (QA)	12-11-2013	Marco Roos, Kristina Hettne	Wrote the discussion and conclusions, added references.

Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the genomics community building activities led by WP6 during the course of the project. We report the strategy that we followed in order to ensure the uptake of Wf4Ever technologies and tools, e.g. the target stakeholders and community leaders, our message, specific activities, how the scientific communities reacted to our efforts, and our future expectations in this regard. We include a measure of the impact of Wf4Ever in the genomics target community, according to the indicators defined in WP8 (D8.2).

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1. Introduction

This report focuses on our progress with regards to the genomics community building activities during the course of the project, while D8.4v2 provides details about WP6 involvement in the various Wf4Ever dissemination activities. Therefore, both documents should be read together. In the following section we give an overview of the status of the use of Wf4Ever-like technology in the genomics community at the start of the project.

Technology for preserving computational experiments in the biomedical domain was at the start of the project (December 2010) in its infancy. We described the situation at the time in detail in WP6 deliverable D6.1, section 1.2. In summary, there was no widely adopted standard for recording and publishing a computational experiment as part of a biological study. Computational components, datasets, tools, etc., were, and still are, sometimes submitted as “supplemental information”, which is typically relatively unstructured. We reported on a number of initiatives addressing certain aspects of preserving computational experiments, such as the public repositories of biological data ArrayExpress¹ and the Gene Expression Omnibus² for gene expression, which require specific metadata to be uploaded with the data, while in turn journals require researchers to submit this type of data into one of these repositories. We also reported that numerous ontologies exist by which data in many public databases are annotated e.g. [1,2], and that the Linked Data principle has increased the popularity of making life science data sets interoperable on the Web [3]. Minimal information models, such as MIAME for gene expression data, help to “harmonize” data, while Semantic Web languages and tools allow meaningful integration across the Web [4,5]. “Nanopublications” provide a basic mechanism by which to expose biological relations, observed or hypothesized, and their provenance [6,7]. Furthermore we mentioned the Concept Wiki³, a recent initiative that aims to provide a community-curated resource of disambiguated concepts to the Semantic Web [8]. For methods and code, we reported on initiatives that allow some form of archiving and sharing, such as BioConductor⁴ for sharing packages in the statistical programming language R, the BioCatalogue⁵ for sharing and annotating Web Services, and myExperiment⁶ for sharing workflows, and the existence of an active bioinformatics user community around workflow technology, with Taverna⁷, Galaxy⁸, Kepler⁹ and GenePattern¹⁰ as popular players on the open-access workbench provider scene. Since none of these efforts met the demands of performing increasingly complex integrative analysis, while upholding scientific principles such as reproducibility and the preservation of experimental materials and methods as evidence for our findings, we develop the concept of a Research Object (RO) in this project. From a biological perspective this is a structured container for the

1 <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/>

2 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>

3 <http://conceptwiki.org>

4 <http://www.bioconductor.org/>

5 <http://www.biocatalogue.org/>

6 <http://www.myexperiment.org/>

7 <http://www.taverna.org.uk/>

8 <http://galaxyproject.org/>

9 <https://kepler-project.org/>

10 <http://www.broadinstitute.org/cancer/software/genepattern>

materials and methods involved in a computational experiment. The ROs collect and organize the diversity of information needed to support a research finding, and can be exposed to colleagues and peers similar to sharing a notebook or a published methods section.

In section 2 we summarize our strategy to ensure the uptake of Wf4Ever technologies and tools. Section 3 zooms in on the core element of our approach, namely the development of Best Practices for workflow design and RO creation. Section 4 describes concrete community engagement activities, while section 5 is dedicated to reflections on our chosen approach and our expectations for the future with regards to the uptake of Wf4Ever technology and tools by the genomics community. Finally, we state our conclusions in section 6.

2. Methodological approach

In this section we describe the strategy that we followed in order to ensure uptake of Wf4Ever technology in the genomics community. We report on identified target stakeholders and community leaders, and our message. Our strategy can be summarized as follows:

1. Identify local, national and international target stakeholders
2. Develop tools and content
3. Disseminate results
4. Establish collaborations for during the course of the project and beyond

We identified local, national, and international target stakeholders. Local stakeholders were defined within the LUMC as research groups already using workflow technology, i.e. the Department of Parasitology: FTICR- and high-throughput proteomics group, and the Department of Human Genetics: Genetics and Systems Biology of the Metabolic Syndrome and Neurogenetics group. Our message to these groups was that we would support them by acting as a hub. We would relay their questions about workflow platforms and technology and report on their research using workflows to the Wf4Ever team, while in turn providing them with updates on the Wf4Ever technology development, and support their use of workflow technology by developing Best Practices for workflow design [9]. Initial face-to-face meetings followed by e-mail correspondence to report significant progress was judged to be sufficient to keep the line short with the FTICR- and high-throughput proteomics group, while the Genetics and Systems Biology of the Metabolic Syndrome group and the Neurogenetics group already had agreed to be deeper involved by providing the two case studies on the Metabolic Syndrome (MetS) and Huntington's disease (HD) and develop workflows for these (see deliverable D6.3v3). Concerning the MetS and HD case studies, two-weekly meetings were judged necessary to ensure progress.

Regarding national stakeholders, we focused primarily on the Netherlands Bioinformatics Center (NBIC) (see also deliverable D8.4v2), and the community around HD. Our message to these stakeholders can be summarized as: 1) contribute to standards by developing state-of-the-art workflows following our proposed Best Practices for workflow design, 2) contribute to tooling by providing support for running workflows independent of platform, i.e. t2web [10] and biosemantics Web Services¹¹, and 3) contribute to knowledge by reporting on progress on RO model and technology developments. We judged a direct line to the NBIC organization as crucial to ensure uptake of Wf4Ever technology in the Netherlands. In line with this decision, we participated in the monthly meetings of the NBIC interoperability task force, thus connecting Wf4Ever to interoperability activities in the Netherlands, of which several have an international outreach (see also deliverable D8.4v2). In the second year of the Wf4Ever project, WP6 leader Marco Roos became the leader of this task force. Active participation in meetings and conferences organized by the NBIC and the HD community was also part of our national genomics community building strategy.

Our primary international target stakeholder was the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB), the leading professional society for computational biology, which organizes a number of well-renown

¹¹ <https://www.biocatalogue.org/services/3330>

conferences including the world's largest bioinformatics/computational biology conference: the International Conference on Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology (ISMB). We also identified the annual international Semantic Web Applications and Tools for life sciences (SWAT4LS) workshop as an important venue, since it brings together researchers, both developers and users, from the various fields of biology, bioinformatics and computer science, to discuss goals, current limits and real experiences in the use of semantic, web-based technologies in the life sciences and biomedical informatics. Our messages to these stakeholders were similar to the national stakeholders with regards to development of Best Practices and contribution to standards, and the communication took place by accepted presentations, posters, publications and workshops (see Appendix B and Appendix C). Recently, we initiated a collaboration between developers of the ISA model ('Investigation, Study, Assay') [11], the Nanopublication model¹², and the RO model, and employees of the GigaScience journal¹³ as target users, as a means to bring communities together who develop and use complementary models for capturing scholarly communication in the '-omics' domain.

¹² <http://nanopub.org/nschema>

¹³ <http://www.gigasciencejournal.com>

3. Best Practices for Workflow Design

Our core work for genomics community building involves the development of Best Practices for workflow design and RO creation, with the aim to encourage workflow re-use and prevent decay. They were also instrumental for the development of tooling that facilitates RO creation, such as the checklist service. WP6 leads this work, which was first presented at the 2nd BioVeL Workshop on taxonomic and phylogenetic workflows¹⁴ in May 2012. The biodiversity researchers, who had just started using workflows, were interested in hearing what we consider Best Practices for creating workflows. Our proposed Best Practices were based on past experiences, mostly in the bioinformatics field, insights from Wf4Ever, and general background in experimental science/biology and computer science. The positive feedback following the BioVeL workshop encouraged us to continue to refine the Best Practices and use them actively when developing our own workflows and ROs. This work led to a conference proceedings paper and presentation at the SWAT4LS workshop¹⁵ in December the same year, where we presented the final 10 Best Practices, example workflows, and how the work fitted into the current version of the RO model and tools (see Appendix C). The Best Practices are summarized below.

1. **Make a sketch workflow** (to help design the overall data flow and workflow aims, and to identify the tools and data resources required at each stage)
2. **Use modules** (to make it easier for other scientists to reuse parts of a workflow at a later date)
3. **Think about the output** (workflows can be used to integrate and visualise data as well as for analysing it, so one should consider how the results will be presented easily to the user)
4. **Provide input and output examples** (to show the format of input required for the workflow and the type of output that should be produced)
5. **Annotate** (accurately describing what individual services do, what data they consume and produce, and the aims of the workflow are all essential for reuse)
6. **Make it executable from outside the local environment** (workflows are more reusable if they can be executed from anywhere)
7. **Choose services carefully** (some services are more reliable or more stable than others, and examining which are the most popular can assist with this process)
8. **Reuse existing workflows** (if a workflow has been tried, tested and published, reusing it can save a significant amount of time and resource)
9. **Test and Validate** (to understand the limitations of workflows, and to monitor changes to underlying services)
10. **Advertise and Maintain** (others can only reuse it if it is accessible and if it is updated when required, due to changes in underlying services).

¹⁴ <http://www.biovel.eu/index.php/events/22-events/biovel-meetings/43-ms6-workshop>

¹⁵ <http://www.swat4ls.org/workshops/paris2012/>

The Best Practices were also presented at the NBIC BioAssist programmers meeting in February 2013. Again, encouraging response from the community motivated us to further develop this work (see also Appendix A). We submitted a manuscript to the Journal of Biomedical Semantics in May 2013 describing our efforts in this regards, which is currently under revision. An important element to community uptake is trust. We have tried to build trust by following the Best Practices ourselves and referring to them when we present our workflows at conferences and in journal publications (see Appendix B and Appendix C).

4. Community engagement activities

We here report on the activities undertaken to ensure genomics user community uptake. Relevant key performance indicators were defined in D8.2. For Biologists these were the following: research papers in conferences and journals that use Wf4Ever, and for Bioinformaticians the following: engagement in events, Wf4Ever promoted to scientists, papers and demos. Presentations and research papers in conferences and journals are listed in Appendix B and C. User interaction activities are reported below.

To strengthen the local biologist and bioinformatician workflow user core, we organized user meetings at the LUMC (November 22, 2011) and at UNIMAN with the Taverna/myGrid team (February 4, 2012). Targeting the national bioinformatics community, the t2web application for running Taverna workflows on the web was demoed at the 7th edition of the Netherlands Bioinformatics Conference (April 23-24, 2012) as an Application Showcase, and won the Showcase Award. We led a hands-on session at the NBIC BioAssist programmers meeting (February 8, 2013), where users could play around with our BioSemantics workflows¹⁶, Web Services¹⁷, and supporting tools¹⁸. We further demoed our Wf4Ever-supported workflows at the 8th edition of the Netherlands Bioinformatics Conference (April 16, 2013) as an Application Showcase. Targeting PhD students, we integrated ROs in the NBIC PhD course on Managing and Integrating Information in the Life Sciences¹⁹ (17-21 June, 2013). On the international level, we organized a technology track and a workshop at the 21st edition of the ISMB/ECCB conference (July 22, 2013) where we showcased current state-of-the art in publication formats explicitly created for digital environments, including ROs nanopublications and ISA.

¹⁶ <http://www.myexperiment.org/packs/368>

¹⁷ <https://www.biocatalogue.org/services/3330>

¹⁸ <http://workflow.biosemantics.org/t2web/workflow/3006>

¹⁹ <http://www.nbic.nl/education/nbic-phd-school/nbic-phd-school-course-portfolio/managing-and-integrating-information-in-the-life-sciences/>

5. Discussion and future work

At the start of the project there was no clear candidate model for aggregating and annotating the materials and methods of digital experiments in the genomics domain, particularly for workflow-based experiments. The RO model provides such a candidate. Although a workflow definition by itself is a form of captured method, especially when it contains user documentation, it is typically not sufficient for peers to understand a complete experiment and its results. The RO model now allows us to aggregate the complete scholarly communication that genomics researchers find necessary for understanding a digital experiment, reuse the methods or reproduce its results. The reference tooling that wf4ever produced allows us to show how this model can be used in tools such as a bioinformatics workbench (Taverna), and tools developed for sharing digital research artefacts, such as myExperiment and digital library software. In particular, RO-oriented software modules, such as the checklist service, demonstrate how such tools can be enhanced to produce higher quality objects, i.e. for preserving high-quality research objects.

Several users have experimented with the reference tooling to create and browse ROs, including our local users, and stakeholders such as from the GigaScience journal and the ISA developer team. In addition, the RO model is taken up by the scholarly communication community, including the genomics part of that community. The combination with the ISA model is particularly interesting, because it already has a substantial community of followers in the '-omics' domain. Locally, creating ROs is now considered the mechanism of choice for preserving computational experiments. We are taking initiatives to include preservation of computational research via the combination of RO, ISA, and Nanopublication in new projects. At the national level, "digital study capture" will be a standard recommendation of the Data Integration and Stewardship Centre (DISC)²⁰, the Dutch node of Elixir²¹, which will closely follow the development of RO models and tools via the W3C community group²². At the international level, our collaboration with the ISA and nanopublication communities, where the RO model is the primary candidate for aggregation and annotation as a complement to these models, ensures limiting redundancy between future versions of these models, which would be undesirable for the genomics community. For a detailed description of our future activities, see deliverable D1.5v2, section 4.2.2. Wf4Ever was also instrumental in developing the W3C-recommended provenance exchange model²³. Provenance is a common aspect of the aforementioned models.

In terms of scholarly communication a paradigm shift is made possible by the application of ROs. We experienced that papers can become the complement of Research Objects, rather than the other way around. The narrative can only capture part of the research. In digital research large parts of the required components for evaluation, reuse, and reproduction can be captured automatically or semi-automatically. The narrative can focus on highlighting the main interpretation of researchers, while pointing readers to various parts of the Research Object for more documentation, data, and executable components. In addition,

²⁰ <http://www.dtls.nl/dtl/programmes/disc.html>

²¹ <http://www.elixir-europe.org>

²² <http://www.w3.org/community/rosc/>

²³ <http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

RO evolution provides a means of updating previous work, following the paradigm that research is rarely truly 'finished'. The Best Practices for workflow design, augmented by the process of creating ROs, have led to a different working methodology. Computational biologists were used to compiling materials (scripts, datasets, etc.) on their local hard discs in a relatively unstructured manner, and the Best Practices enforce a more complete and more structured aggregation of materials. In quantifiable ways, we have interacted with users at user events (see section 4), provided communication material (see Appendix A), presented our work at different meetings and conferences (see Appendix B), and documented our processes and experiences through conference proceedings and submitted journal publications (see Appendix C).

We envision that the distinction between genomics study capture and genomics workbenches will gradually disappear. The notion of "sticky notes" that is enabled by compliance with the RO model, allows metadata to be harvested while going from tool to tool. This provides an additional layer of interoperability and study capture for popular tools such as Taverna, Galaxy, myExperiment and Genome Space. By also following Best practices for workflow creation, high quality research objects can be preserved that guarantee a higher probability that research results can be reproduced.

6. Conclusions

The RO model has matured into a candidate model for aggregating the complete scholarly communication that genomics researchers find necessary for understanding a digital experiment, reusing the methods or reproducing its results. Workflow re-use is encouraged and workflow decay is prevented by following the 10 Best Practices for workflow design, and Wf4Ever tooling such as the checklist service facilitates RO creation. Locally, creating ROs is now considered the mechanism of choice for preserving computational experiments, and we are taking initiatives to include preservation of computational research via the combination of RO, ISA, and Nanopublication in new projects.

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Appendix A – Communication material

- Best Practices for Workflow Design presentation [SlideShare²⁴, 4728 views as of November 4, 2013]
- Concept Profile Mining Web Services [BioCatalogue²⁵, 1553 views as of November 4, 2013]
- Concept Profile Mining Workflows [myExperiment²⁶, 39 views as of November 4, 2013]

²⁴ <http://www.slideshare.net/khettne/10-best-practices-for-workflow-design>

²⁵ <https://www.biocatalogue.org/services/3330>

²⁶ <http://www.myexperiment.org/packs/368>

Appendix B – Presentations at conferences

- **2012-04-24** 7th NBIC Conference, Lunteren, the Netherlands. Eleni Mina, Reinout van Schouwen, Kostas Karasavvas, Kristina Hettne, Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Pernette J. Verschure, Christine Chichester, Barend Mons, Willeke van Roon-Mom, Marco Roos: **e-Science in bioinformatics: enabling the reuse of methods while unravelling the epigenetic factors of Huntington's Disease.**
- **2012-05-11** 2nd BioVeL Workshop on taxonomic and phylogenetic workflows, Gothenburg, Sweden. Kristina Hettne, Katy Wolstencroft, Carole Goble, Marco Roos: **10 Best Practices for Workflow Design.**
- **2012-05-23** 6th European Conference on Rare Diseases and Orphan Products, Brussels, Belgium. Marco Roos, Erik A. Schultes, Barend Mons: **Speeding up research with the Semantic Web.**
- **2012-05-23** 4th International Workshop on Science Gateways for Life Sciences (IWSG-Life 2012), Amsterdam, the Netherlands. Kostas Karasavvas, Marco Roos: **Opening new gateways to workflows for scientists.**
- **2012-11-28** SWAT4LS 2012, Paris, France. Kristina Hettne, Katherine Wolstencroft, Khalid Belhajjame, Carole Goble, Eleni Mina, Harish Dharuri, David De Roure, Lourdes Verdes-Montenegro, Julian Garrido and Marco Roos: **Best Practices for workflow design: how to prevent workflow decay.**
- **2012-12-09** 2nd ISCB-Asia/SCCG 2012, ShenZhen, China. Marco Roos: **Now that Newton's work is well preserved: how about yours?**
- **2013-07-21** ISMB/ECCB 2013, Berlin, Germany. Technical track. Jun Zhao, Mark Thompson, Kristina Hettne, Katy Wolstencroft, Erik A. Schultes, Mark Wilkinson, Barend Mons, Carole Goble, Marco Roos: **Technology for sharing methods and data of computational experiments in a digital era.**

Appendix C – Publications

Posters

- **2011-12-07** SWAT4LS 2011, London, England. Kristina Hettne, Khalid Belhajjame, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Matthew Gamble, Oscar Corcho, Graham Klyne, Sean Bechhofer, Marco Roos: **Workflow forever: Semantic Web Semantic models and tools for preserving and digitally publishing computational experiments.**
- **2012-07-15** ISMB 2012, Long Beach, California, USA. Kostas Karasavvas, Christine Chichester, Eleni Mina, Reinout van Schouwen, Kristina Hettne, Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Pernelle Verschure, Barend Mons, Willeke van Roon-Mom, Marco Roos: **Enabling the reuse of methods while unraveling the epigenetic factors of Huntington's Disease.**
- **2013-04-16** NBIC 2013, Lunteren, the Netherlands. Eelke van der Horst, Marco Roos, Kristina Hettne: **Emc2Skos: a SKOS conversion app for the ErasmusMC Ontology format.**
- **2013-07-20** BioLINK Special Interest Group, In Association with ISMB/ECCB 2013, Berlin, Germany. Kristina M. Hettne, Harish Dharuri, Reinout van Schouwen, Peter A.C. 'T Hoen, Barend Mons and Marco Roos: **Explaining genome-wide association study results using concept profile analysis and the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes pathway database.**
- **2013-07-21** ISMB/ECCB 2013, Berlin, Germany. Eelke van der Horst, Marco Roos, Kristina Hettne: **Workflows and Services for Concept Profile Generation.**

Conference/Workshop proceedings

- David De Roure, Khalid Belhajjame, Paolo Missier, José Manuel Gómez-Pérez, Raúl Palma, José Enrique Ruiz, Kristina Hettne, Marco Roos, Graham Klyne, Carole Goble: **Towards the Preservation of Scientific Workflows.** In Proc 8th International Conference on Preservation of Digital Objects (iPRES 2011), Singapore, Singapore.
- Kristina Hettne, Katherine Wolstencroft, Khalid Belhajjame, Carole Goble, Eleni Mina, Harish Dharuri, David De Roure, Lourdes Verdes-Montenegro, Julian Garrido and Marco Roos: **Best Practices for workflow design: how to prevent workflow decay.** In Proc 5th international Semantic Web Applications and Tools for Life Sciences (SWAT4LS) workshop 2012, Paris, France.
- Jun Zhao, Jose Manuel Gomez-Perez, Khalid Belhajjame, Graham Klyne, Esteban Garcia-Cuesta, Aleix Garrido, Kristina Hettne, Marco Roos, David De Roure, Carole Goble. **Why workflows break- Understanding and combating decay in Taverna Workflows.** In Proc IEEE 8th International Conference on eScience 2012, Chicago, USA.
- Jun Zhao, Graham Klyne, Piotr Holubowicz, Raúl Palma, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Kristina Hettne, José Enrique Ruiz, Marco Roos, Kevin Page, José Manuel Gómez-Pérez, David De Roure, Carole Goble: **RO-Manager: A Tool for Creating and Manipulating Research Objects to Support**

Reproducibility and Reuse in Sciences. In Proc 2nd Linked Science Workshop at ISWC 2012, Boston, USA.

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